

Aesthetics and Psychological Aspects of Indian Classical Dance Forms: A Comparative Study

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Abstract:

Indian classical dance forms embody a rich confluence of aesthetics and psychological elements, reflecting the cultural and spiritual ethos in India. This research will explore the aspects of aesthetics and psychological impishness by examining their historical context, performance styles and also psychological effects on performers and audience. Through rigorous training and disciplined practices, dancers achieve a state of heightened awareness and emotional catharsis, promoting mental well-being and spiritual fulfilment. This study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of aesthetics, rhythm, melody, expression and all classical dance forms that contribute to cultural identity and also a powerful medium for psychological exploration for well-being.

Keywords: Aesthetics, Psychological Elements, Spirituality, Audience Engagement, Emotional Catharsis, Sample Size.

Music, obviously inseparable from dance, has had a pronounced influence on the existence of dance compositions. Evolution of the musical forms in the music field and their adaptation into the dance tradition, itself demands an in-depth study. The *lakṣaṇa* and the *lakṣya* have coexisted, in their documentation and evolution respectively. The oral/practising traditions have been true repositories in maintaining, retaining and enlivening the practices, as is especially observed in *Bharatanāṭya* down the praxis. Being a practitioner and a teacher of the Kolar *Sampradāya* of the Karnataka classical dance tradition, the practice and performance of several unfamiliar pieces like “*Thāya, prabandha, sulādi* and alike, posed many questions. The quest to unearth the reasons and the evolution of such compositions

ignited the search and a self-imposed goal was set to revive, restore and relive through a research perspective. An in-depth study of the historicity of dance compositions, through four hundred years post-Vijayanagar times, was undertaken. One such intriguing composition which drew enormous attention was *ṭhāya*.

“*Ṭhāya* - is one of the components of the four ‘*daṇḍi-s*’ described by Venkaṭamakḥin in his *caturadaṇḍi prakāśika* (1620 AD) - *gīta*, *prabandha*, *ālāpa* and *ṭhāya*” (Arathi Rao).

The South Indian classical music forms of the pre-modern era were based on the above four forms. “The earliest textual mention of the four melodic forms in one sequence is available in Ramamaṭya’s *Svaramēḷa Kalanidhi* of 1550 A.D.” (Seeta 46: 1979). It can be observed that all genres of classical music were classified under these four forms exclusively. Tannappacharya, a musician-par-excellence, documents these four musical forms during his time in the 16th Century. Later Venkatamakḥi, his protege, a competent musicologist of the 17th Century, called the four musical forms as the ‘*Catura daṇḍi*’ or four pillars of South Indian music. Venkatamakḥi, also asserts that his mentor, Tanappacharya, is an authority in *Ṭhāya Lakṣaṇa*. “Many seminal developments in South Indian music took place during the Vijayanagara period. *Ālāpa* and *ṭhāya* – two musical forms emerged in the Vijayanagara period”. (Arati Rao Journal of the Music Academy Madras, Chennai, Vol 87: 2016). The studies confirm the practising tradition of *Ṭhāya* in the music realm since the early mediaeval period. “*Ṭhāya* was in practice in both Andhra and Karnāṭaka regions well before Venkatamakḥi and Tannappacharya times” (Satyanarayana preface: 2006)¹

The historicity reveals the fact that the origin and practice of rendering the tetrad musical modes was much before Venkatamakḥi and it continued till the time of King Tulaja and the Maratha period in the late 19th Century. It is understood by the illustrations of

¹ “*Āturadaṇḍi prakāśika of Venkatamakḥi*”-critical edition by Dr.R. Satyanarayana

Saṅgīta Sārāmruta, that *Ṭhāyas* and *Ālāpas* were utilised to perfect a particular *rāga* by the musicians. They were constructed in a particular format to facilitate the purpose. “*Caturadaṇḍi prakāśika* becomes highly significant that it is an indication of scientific and practical rendition of illustrating a *rāga* through four channels of expression” (Seeta 25: 1980). The *Thanjavur* Saraswathi Mahal Library preserves the *Ṭhāya* and *ālāpa* illustrations in manuscript form. The manuscripts have been brought out in the printed form in the mid-20th century by scholars like Dr. Raghavan, Dr. R. Satyanarayana and Dr. Seeta with an able team of the library officials.

“*Ṭhāyam* is a composition, resembling the *gīta* in its general structure. Its distinctive feature, is the presence of *pāṭha* or *śollakattu*. It belongs to the *abhyāsa gāna*, Puranadara Dasa and Ventamakhi have composed many *Ṭhāyas*”. (Sambamurthy 235: 1998). “In the treatise, page 72, of Tulaja, states that illustrations from the old traditional *Āturadaṇḍi pieces* are given to determine the occurrence of permissible *prayogās*, *tānās*, *murchanās* in the definition of *rāga svarupa*” (Seeta, *ibid*).

आरोहावरोहमूर्च्छनातानयोरयं संदर्भो ऽत्र
संगच्छते ऽयं संदर्भो न संगच्छत इत्येतन्निश्चयार्थं प्राचीनगीतप्रबन्धठायालाप-
रूपचतुर्दण्डीसूलादिप्रभृत्युदाहरणलेखनेन स्फुटं यथा भवति तथा लिख्यते ।

One can comprehend, by the above statement that the *Ṭhāya*, was very much in existence in the colonial/modern period as a *prayōga*, and also as a concert composition in the music realm. The *gīta*, *Ṭhāya*, *ālāpa* and *prabandha* are special features of Tulaja’s *rāga Lakṣaṇas*. (*Rāga* chapters of *Saṅgīta Sārāmruta* 264: religiousdocbox. com).

Dhāya Prayōga - r g r m - s n r - p n m - p m r m m p - m p n n s - n s
 r m m p n - m p p s s - s s n m - p n p p m - m p m r g r s -

Prabhandha Prayōga - r n p n p p m r - g r s s n p g r s s

One can find and identify the manuscripts with illustrations of *Thāya* in the Telugu section of TMSSML-11580-D888 and D887-11579- a copy is illustrated here transliterated into Kannada:

Sthāya - Dhaya- Thāya – a discussion:

The Sanskrit word ‘*Sthāya*’ got transformed to *Thāya*, the characteristic grouping of *svara-s*” as illustrated above. *Saṅgīta Ratnākara* has prescribed *Sthāya* to around ninety *rāgas*, which eventually became *Thāya* as per studies conducted by music historians. *Sthāya* and *Thāya* are synonymous in Parshwadeva’s *Saṅgīta Samayasāra* (13th Century), and it is seen as a melodic structure which later assumed a standardised musical form in the 16th Century as understood from references of *Svaramēḷa Kalānidhi*, *Caturadaṇḍi prakāśika*, *Saṅgīta Sarāmrutha* and *Saṅgīta Sampradāya pradarśini*. (16th to 20th Century).

Venkatamakhi in his *Caturadaṇḍi prakāśika*, chapter seven - 1 to 7 *ślokas* describes the *lakṣaṇa* or the rendering style of *Ṭhāyas*. The paper copies in *Devanāgarī* of palm leaf Telugu manuscripts from the TMSSM Library, *Thanjavur* contain a good number of *ṭhaya* and *ālāpa* notations. In *Saṅgīta Sārāmruta*, Tulaja uses the term ‘*Dhāya*’ instead of *Ṭhāya*. Historical evidences prove the connotation of all three ‘*Sthāya - Dhāya - Ṭhāya*’ as similar, synonyms in the music realm. An important finding, crucial to this paper “in these manuscripts, for both *ṭhāyas* and *ālāpas*, there are two types of notations: those that have ‘*nam-tam*’ syllables and those that do not;” (Arathi: *ibid*).

Structure of *Ṭhāya*:

Ṭhāya belongs to the *rāga ālāpana paddhati* as per studies. The *Ṭhāyas* are pure musical forms with no lyrical structure and no bound rhythm and the musician is allowed to improvise according his/her own creativity. “The *Ṭhāya* is very much like the the *ālāpana*, the distinction lies in that the former is performed with *svara* and *nom-tom* syllables, latter without *svara*.” (Seeta 1979)². The manuscripts in the custody of of *Thanjavur*’s Saraswathi Mahal Library, demonstrates the illustrative *lakṣya* formats for *rāga lakṣaṇa*. The *Ṭhāya* format is observed with ‘*Nam tom / tam*’ syllables in sources. “*Ālāpa* and *ṭhaya* are non-lyrical musical compositions (with no *tāḷa*) referred to in various musicological texts from the Vijayanagara period onwards.” (Arathi Rao)³

The *nam-tam* syllables are woven as per the *svara-s* or notations in a particular prescribed format as per technical manuals. Though it is not a predetermined structure for a rendition, there are rules laid out for creating the patterns. A particular style of ascending scale and descending scale is to be practised. Dr Seeta explains in her conference paper, that the *sthāyi svara* (basic note identified in the octave) forms the strong base for further melodic

² Journal of Madras University -1979-Seminar on musical forms- Article- *THAYA* – Dr. Seeta

³ Journal of the Madras Music Academy, Chennai, Vol 87 -2016

elaboration. From the chosen *sthāyi* to the fourth note in ascending scale and similarly from the *tāra sthāyi* descending to the fourth note at the *mandra sthāyi* and further to the initial *sthāyi svāra*, is usually the practised pattern. The *Lakṣaṇas* for *Ṭhāya* are documented by both Govinda Dikshitar and Venkatamakhi along with *rāga lakṣyas*. *Ṭhāyas*, according to the laid down rules, are rendered with gradation from *śadja* and *mandra* to *madhya* and *madhya* to *tāra sthāyi* and further in reverse order as conclusion.

नाट ॥ " सप्तमनिपम । रिगमप । धनिष । सनि
 आशितम् । तमना अनम् । त अनम् । नअअ । नम्
 प । माप्या । सस्सासा । माप्यापा । सास्सासा ॥ - ॥ प ।
 न । ताँङ्गा । तन्नानाम् । ताङ्गाना । ६ ना ना ॥ - ॥ त ।
 सप्तम । सप्तम । सप्त । सरिसस । धनिष । ससनि । पसनि
 नम्ल । नम्ल । नम्ल । नअनम् । नअअ । नम्ल । तम्ल
 सनिप । सनिप । सनिप । प्यमप । मम । रिगमप । धनिष ।
 अनम् । तम्ल । तन ६ । नम्ल । नम् । नअनम् । तम्ल ।
 धनिष । मपधनिष । सनिप । माप्या । सस्सासा । माप्यापा ।
 नम्ल । तअअअअ । नम्ल । तम्ल । नननाम् । ताम्लनना ।

1. *Ṭhāya* with *nam-tam* syllables *nāṭa rāga Ṭhāya* - Manuscript illustrations - Excerpts from *Saṅgīta Sudha* of Govinda Dikshitar. (Courtesy: Dr Arathi Rao)

"ठायम्" ससनिप । धनिषसनि - धनिषरिसस । ध - स ।
 सनिप । धनिषरिष । ममरि । सप्तधनिष । सनिप । पससपम -
 । मममरि । सरिसस । धनिष । सनिप । पसससरी । ध । ममरि ।
 सरिसस । धनिषसनिप । ममरिस । धनिषसनिप । मपसनिप ।

2. *Ṭhāya* without *nam-tam* syllables from *Saṅgīta Sampradāya Pradarshini*.

It appears in the example above, that the notation starts from the *tāra śadja*, touches *mandra sthāyi* and goes back to *tāra śadja* in culmination – the above format suits the explanation by Dr. Seeta. It is interesting to note that one of them, which is a group of *ṭhāya-s*

of *nāṭa rāga*, has *nam-tam* syllables. This indicates that *nam-tam* syllables may not apply only to vocal music in all cases”. (Arathi rao: ibid) This observation leads to understand that *Ṭhāyas* were an integral part of instrumental music. *Ālāpa* and *Ṭhāyas* were applied both to vocal music - *Gāthra daṇḍi* and instrumental music – *Veena* playing *Jantra daṇḍi*, as per the readings on the subject.

Form and content of *Ṭhāya*:

The form of *Ṭhāya* reveals a melodic aesthetic structure, when sung, creating a serene aura and a relaxed ambience experienced by both the singer and the audience. The exposition of the syllables rendered from one octave to another and back, brings in a calm and composed occurrence. The content of the composition is a challenge for the singer, as it involves singing of notation and parallel *nam-tam* syllables, with the right intonation, voice modulation and pitch. Dr. Seeta elaborates, that *gamaka* (aesthetic shaking of voice or *Kampana*); *kaku* (tonal variation); *alankara* (decorative tonal patterns) and *sthāyāvaga* (dynamic melodic phrase), are essential features of *rāga Lakṣaṇa* and important in *Ṭhāya* delineation.

In the 18th Century, the South Indian classical dance tradition adapted the *Ṭhāya* into the dance repertoire. “*Ṭhāyas* were widely used and experimented independent musical forms”. (Satyanarayana 392: 2006). It seems to have been performed as a dance composition with only *svara* patterns and *nam-tom* syllables. As per historical records of the courts of the Thanjavur Nayaks, all the four melodic forms were adapted to dance and performed. “It is said Madhuravani, a dancer received *kanakābhisekam* from King Raghunatha Nayaka for her proficiency in rendering the *caturadaṇḍi* pieces namely *gīta*, *ālāpa*, *Ṭhāya* and *prabandha*” (Seeta 24: 1980).

Ṭhāya- Adaptation from the Saṅgīta parampara to the Nṛtya parampara ('Bharatanāṭya'):

The *Ṭhāya*, with the *nam-tam* syllables as an adaptation into the dance repertoire, is the subject to be discussed next. The music *parampara* composition was adapted into the performance repertoire of *Nṛtya parampara*. A 1964 publication, *Ādi bharata kala manjari*, by Tanjore Kittappa Pillai and K.C. Shivanandam, documents a few *Ṭhāya (dāyam)* with music notations and *nam-tam* syllables in *rāgas gauḷa, varāḷi* and *nāṭa*. This is a print publication, exclusively of erstwhile dance compositions, lost down the generations, revived for posterity by the legendary Tanjore masters. It is understood that so far not found records of a *Ṭhāya* performance in the recent times in the Thanjavur classical dance tradition. K. P. S. Chennai Sivakumar, son of K.C. Shivanandam, shares that, danseuse Vyjayantimala had performed all the four melodic forms in the sixties under the able guidance of Tanjore master K.P. Kittappa Pillai. He further adds, that *Ṭhāyam* was performed as an *nṛtta* composition with rhythmic patterns juxtaposed on the *svara-s* and *nam-tam* syllables.

In the *Kolar Sampradāya* of the Mysore classical dance heritage, sources reveal of the performing tradition of *Ṭhāya* as a part of its temple repertoire. According to the oral tradition, primary sources, the composition was performed as a ritualistic rendition in front of the sanctum sanctorum by the artists in the 19th and early 20th Century in the temples in and around Mysore and Bangalore. Dr. C. Radhakrishna, *Guru* and mentor of Kolar school, for the past four decades, a repository of the old tradition, shared that the *Ṭhāya* was modified into an *nṛtya* composition by adding a lyrical structure to the original form. As the melodic structure of the *Ṭhāya* created the right ambience for a temple dance offering, it was included in the *ālaya* (temple)repertory. “The *nam-tam* syllables of the *Ṭhāya* were replaced by meaningful texts of four or five lines adhering to the canons of the prosody.” (Rajashree 59:

1979)⁴. The antique composition *Ṭhāya*, has traversed in the oral tradition through the genesis to the 20th Century, in the *Kolar Sampradāya* of the present day. A few examples of the *Ṭhāyas* dedicated to Gods *Brahma*, *Vināyaka* and *Mahadeva* are identified in the 19th Century manuscripts of Yajmān Kolar Kittanna. There is another *Ṭhāya* with *Sharada stuti* created by Guru. Radhakrishna, following on the lines of the *Ṭhāyas* of the manuscript.

The adaptation of *Ṭhāya* as an *nṛtya* composition into the *Kolar Sampradāya*:

Ṭhāya, one of the main musical forms of the 18th Century as per classical music *Lakṣaṇa*, was adopted into the classical dance repertoire in the *Kolar Sampradāya*, with a few notable modifications to suit dance interpretation. The *svara-s* or the notations, were utilised as deciphered in the music practice, and suitable lyrics were adapted as per the chosen *tāla* or time measure. The *tālas* were *mishraçāpu* and *adi tālas*, as they provided the desired sustenance of the notations of the *rāga*, for dance delineation and emphasis on the lyrics.

These *Ṭhāyas* of the *Kolar sampradāya*, are of the *nṛtya* category when compared to the *Thanjavur nṛtta* classification. There seems to be a combination of rhythmic structure as well the lyrical format. It provides a good scope to the dancer to perform both the *nṛtta* and the *abhinaya*. The *nam-tam* syllables add melody and a soothing tone to the composition, and the purpose of a ritualistic worship through the lyrics was attained. The lyrics, according to the manuscripts, belong to the devotional verses; *ślokas*; passages from scriptures and *bhakti* - oriented songs - borrowed from contemporary musicians' contributions. *Bramha Ṭhāya* and *Shārada Ṭhāya* are composed with devotional verses taken from the *Upanishads* and *Puranas*. The *Vināyaka* and *Mahadeva Ṭhāyas*, are interspersed with Mysore Sadashivaraya's compositions. The *nam-tam* syllables are sung for entry and exit and as interludes for *nṛtta* delineation. The lyrics are used as verses in the praise of the God and his attributes, good

⁴ Journal of Madras University -1979-Seminar on musical forms- Article - Suḷādis and ugabhogas by K. Srinivasa Iyengar (Rajashree) page-53-60.

over evil exploits are celebrated through *abhinaya*. The rendition of the *Ṭhāya* was structured to be sung in *vilamba kala* or slow rendition (tempo) to suit the temple ambience.

The *Ṭhāya* in the *Kolar Sampradāya*, was a typical temple composition, a part of the worshipping repertoire, according to Dr. C. Radhakrishna, last of the *Nattuvanārs* of the *Kolar Sampradāya*. He added that instruments like the conch, temple bell, cymbals and percussion were part of the music ensemble to create the right devotional ambience. “The *nam-tam* syllables and their melody brought in an ‘*omkara*’ effect in the temples” he explained. In the 1980s, *Guru* Radhakrishna revived the *Ṭhāya* of his tradition and presented it through his disciples.

A comparative study between the *Ṭhāya* of the *Thanjavur* tradition and the Mysore tradition was also undertaken and the process included the revival of the above composition on today’s proscenium, through a research perspective. The varied musical structure and the style of rendition of *Ṭhāya* will surely be a value addition to the present-day Bharathanatya repertoire.

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